

Effect of proposed frontal bone complaint mechanism on its mechanical response as well as on the orbits

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Abstract

A The trauma response is a highly non-linear event. The designs of the osseous anatomical domains are precisely planned allowing room for development and to lessen trauma deleterious effects. Many weakening the craniofacial region provide controlled predefined response. We introduced a new approach to demonstrate the importance of graded damage pattern and how it will affect the fracture toughness. This numerical model demonstrates this concept clearly. These rules should be used to build our knowledge about development and trauma management.

Keywords: Bone fracture, Biomechanics, Craniofacial trauma, Maxillofacial, surgery, Orthopedics, Frontal bone, Compliant mechanism

1. Introduction

T The bone had unique orthotropicity composite structure on multiple scales and levels that could not be made by any human machine [1]. In addition to this orthotropicity we have the unique organic design. One of the important features of the craniofacial structure is the connections between different bones resulting in unique trauma response as well as in the growth [2]. Complaint mechanism include making part of the designed more flexible and other part stiffer [3]. We want to highlight an important anatomical feature of the frontal bone that include weakening and stiffness reduction in a predefined way in a mechanism close to compliant mechanism.

Fracture is a non-linear event [4]. Human anatomy is designed in a way that enables the least possible damage. The most important system encased in the skull is the central nervous system. The importance of other organs could be arranged according to the entitled function. Sight is far away important than speech or listening. Accordingly, the brain and globes should gain a central part in the attention for explanation of the anatomical configurations. The frontal bone had 2 main parts [5]

- Squamous part
- Orbital part

Many mechanical details should be noted when characterize the performance of this bone. The connection of the frontal bone with the ethmoid bone had marked discontinuity representing a weakening of this bone. Many other details should be studied, but in the current paper we will emphasize upon this discontinuity. Olfactory nerve could assume a

different configuration, i.e. single bundle exits the skull through a foramen instead of multiple small openings [6].

2. Method

In all of our models, engineering models have been used, but in this model a model with highly resemblance to the natural model as the design here is critical. The model was solid homogenous isotropic which is in contrast to the orthotropic model with other special weakening entity, namely the frontal sinus

The used FEA simulation software was Altair Simsolid 2021 (Troy, Michigan, USA). Two main boundary conditions were studied, namely static and dynamic. Although static application of the forces will not give an insight into the trauma effect. Rather it would give great insight into the growth.

Figure 1 The individual bones are given different colors

All these anatomical structures and their connections need detailed description which is beyond the scope of this paper. There are many features of anatomy that need investigation, but the large picture is formed from multiple small pieces.

Figure 2 This is a lower oblique view of the isolated frontal bone.

Figure 3 This is a lower oblique view of the isolated frontal bone.

As the anatomy of the skull is complex, numerical simulation analysis results will be difficult to interpret. Accordingly, we had made a replacement the bones attached to the frontal bone by a customized struts that resemble these bones.

Figure 4 The correlation of the coordination system with the results should be done

In the next lines we will explain the basis of the engineering struts used to stabilize the virtual frontal bone. The coordination system in this experiment is clear. This is the actual model in relation to the global coordination system used in the numerical simulation. This is very important to understand the results in relation to the inputs, namely boundary conditions.

Figure 5 The frontal model here had symmetrical halves

Figure 6 Medical view of the skull half give an invaluable insight

Figure 7 Another view of half of our model

These are the main housing bones of the frontal bone. The effect of the housing of the bone on the mechanical response of the bone is equivocal to the bone itself. One of the core key points in Aous theory is *(There are anatomical features that make the bone itself behave as multiple pieces united instead of making the bone response in singularity)*

Figure 8 The frontal bone had been assigned with transparent material to show the adjacent bones

Figure 9 The frontal bone had been assigned with transparent material to show the adjacent bones

In the Figure 8 and Figure 9 frontal bone had been assigned with transparent material. The anatomical house of any bone we want to study should not get less attention especially in representing them as boundary conditions in the case of numerical simulation.

Frontal bone socket is formed mainly from 4 bones [7],

- Parietal
- Zygora
- Maxilla
- Ethmoid

The parietal and zygora are the most robust attachments. Role of the parietal and other bones that house this socket should be understood in the context of stiffness gradient and the purposed graded damage pattern. Concepts of socket should not be preserved for dentition only.

Figure 10 Frontal bone in its engineering housing

Figure 11 Transparent frontal bone in its engineering housing

This is the digital version of the socket. How to simplify the anatomy is a very delicate process and needs special biomechanical insight [8]. The result of the numerical simulation is dependent upon these boundary conditions. The numerical simulation is to observe behavior of the bone itself and the effect of adjacent bones over it and show how this bone affects **other bones when it had an impaction over it**

Figure 12 Although occipital bone affects the response of the frontal bone, but it had no direct bond to it

Figure 13 Overlapping the digital socket with the more realistic natural socket.

Figure 14 The frontal bone had been hidden to show only socket

Figure 15 Socket of the frontal bone could be regarded as an analogue with high fidelity.

Figure 16 the frontal bone had been assigned as transparent so that the socket of the frontal bone could be regarded as an analogue with high fidelity.

To investigate the importance of the central discontinuity of the frontal bone, that is gapped by the cribriform part of the ethmoid bone in the anterior cranial fossa, we had created a rigid mass that represent the continuity in the midline to provide an abnormal model that is an

exact replica of the normal model, but just different in this specific feature. We should emphasize upon the fact that the anatomy in its current scheme represent the ultimate design which is beyond our understanding but our work is to highlight some of the fascinating features of very small part of this anatomy.

Figure 17 The red arrows represent the force and the adjacent region of the frontal bone represent the site that received this force. The yellow region represents the fixed region of the house that invests the frontal bone.

As we stated already, we had done two analyses

1. Static loading to explore more mechanical properties in more details. One of these aspects is the possible deformation under normal daily activity [9]. The last one had not been done as it need new boundary conditions
2. Dynamic loading in a period of 5 millisecond with the same force magnitude as we are dealing with trauma cases in other numerical simulations.

3. Results and discussion

Our frontal bone digital model is an entry to the biomechanics of the craniofacial structures.

Figure 18 This is the displacement resulting from the static analysis of the normal anatomy, without central connection.

The roof of the orbit adjacent to the trauma side clearly represents the higher displacement relative to the contralateral side. We should emphasize upon that in static analysis the representation is not true for the trauma. The growth will be resulted from the deformation associated with the daily functions that is closer to the static changes. The reciprocal deformation that is resulted from the daily activity will lead to enable the growth regions to increase in the predesignated direction of growth.

Figure 19 This is the displacement resulting from the static analysis of the abnormal anatomy, with presence of the central connection.

Higher displacement in the pillars of the contralateral side.

Figure 20 Rear view of the displacement resulting from the static analysis of the abnormal anatomy, with presence of the central connection.

Higher displacement in the pillars of the contralateral side. The metopic suture should be reviewed in all of its stages from this mechanical point of view. These boundary conditions are suited to represent trauma case. Nevertheless, it gives unevaluable perspective about the importance of the anatomical design criteria.

Figure 21 Rear view of the displacement resulting from the static analysis of the abnormal anatomy, with presence of the central connection. The central connecting part is very evident.

Figure 22 This is the displacement resulting from the dynamic analysis of the normal anatomy, without central connection

The color map needs more refinement. This is the same map of the previous figure which shows the high difference between the dynamic and static response. Static response is much greater in magnitude than the dynamic response.

Figure 23 This is the displacement resulting from the dynamic analysis of the abnormal anatomy, with presence of the central connection. The posterior part of the orbital roof is apparent.

Figure 24 Rear view of the displacement resulting from the dynamic analysis of the abnormal anatomy, with presence of the central connection.

Higher displacement in the pillars of the ipsilateral side. The central defect is clearly apparent. Both sides demonstrate a non-uniform distribution of the displacement values distribution revealed by the distribution of the displacement colors map.

Figure 25 Rear view of the displacement resulting from the dynamic analysis of the abnormal anatomy, with presence of the central connection.

Displacement is more uniformly distributed on both sides.

Figure 26 Static response of the normal anatomy.

Evaluation of the virtual socket is very important to investigate the effect of the design criteria upon the total performance. The performance of the biologic systems should be evaluated by multiple means. The frontal bone is derived from intramembranous route, making it more suitable to transfer the stress more posteriorly where the actual regions that derive the craniofacial growth are residing.

Figure 27 The displacement in the housing bones of the abnormal frontal bone model. The connecting engineering piece is evident.

Figure 28 Dynamic displacement in the case of normal bone. The highest displacement is in the central region.

Figure 29 The presence of the central connecting abnormality will affect the bone response greatly.

Figure 30 The strain in the normal anatomy in the case of static analysis of the normal model show slightly higher at the lateral side at the side of trauma.

Figure 31 The strain in the normal anatomy in the case of static analysis of the normal model shows slightly higher values at the central region.

Figure 32 Strain in the case of static boundary conditions

It is worthy to note this results as many very similar genetic conditions produce diverse manifestations. The craniofacial regions had very complex loadings with associated diverse phenotypes.

Figure 33 This is the strain map in the case of dynamic study. The presence of the central defect spares the contralateral side of the frontal bone from trauma.

Figure 34 Strain in the case of abnormal anatomy in the dynamic status had less central involvement bore extension to the other side.

Figure 35 Strain at the dynamic analysis.

Figure 36 Strain at the dynamic analysis. The model with connecting object is clear.

1	3.7629e+00
2	7.5258e+00
3	7.7989e+00
4	7.9632e+00
5	8.3069e+00
6	8.6185e+00
7	8.6538e+00
8	9.3670e+00
9	1.0444e+01
10	1.1068e+01

Figure 37 These are the frequencies of the connected model resulted from Modal analysis shows generally higher eigenfrequencies of the abnormal model.

1	3.7866e+00
2	6.7537e+00
3	7.6980e+00
4	7.9868e+00
5	8.2834e+00
6	8.5803e+00
7	8.6246e+00
8	9.3302e+00
9	1.0436e+01
10	1.0941e+01

Figure 38 Modal analysis shows generally lower eigenfrequencies of the non-connected abnormal model.

No connection had lower eigenfrequencies. Again, this is linear material without any dumping mean. Nevertheless, higher frequencies had different distribution due to slight change in the design.

Figure 39 Different fields of the displacement will show different aspects of the performance. This is the X field displacement form the static analysis of the model without connection (normal anatomy model).

Figure 40 In the case of connection, static analysis shows X field displacement extend well into the other side.

Figure 41 In the case of dynamic analysis, the X field displacement color map showed more blunt differences, but still there is clear difference agree with what we already had pointed to.

Figure 42 Dynamic analysis X field displacement.

Figure 43 X filed displacement from the dynamic analysis of the normal anatomy.

Figure 44 X field displacement from the dynamic analysis of the abnormal anatomy.

Figure 45 Z field displacement from the static analysis shows clearly a big difference. In the case where the connection in the center will govern the frontal bone to behave in total, but the central discontinuity makes it more flexible and behave as it formed from multiple parts.

Figure 46 Z field displacement from the static analysis of the abnormal model

Figure 47 In the dynamic status the Z field displacement tells another story.

It is apparent that the non-continuity at the center produces the ability to deform more. The roof of the calvaria is also affected by this anatomical feature.

Figure 48 In the dynamic status the Z field displacement of the abnormal model

Figure 49 The upscaled deformation of the resulted geometry after loading reveal the relative displacement between the orbits at both right and left sides.

Figure 50 Exaggerated deformation could be done in the FEA software to get an excellent visual demonstration of the deformation resulted from the loading.

Figure 51 Deformation of the normal anatomy model.

Figure 52 Deformation of the abnormal anatomy model

Figure 53 Exaggerated deformity superimposed on the pre-loaded normal model.

Figure 54 Exaggerated deformity superimposed on the pre-loaded abnormal connected model.

Figure 55 Superimposition of the deformed model on the original model without central continuity.

Figure 56 Superimposition of the deformed model on the original model with central continuity.

Figure 57 Von Mises criteria derived from the static analysis of the normal anatomy model.

Figure 58 Von Mises criteria derived from the static analysis. It is an agreed criteria of failure in the engineering community, but its application should be scrutinized carefully when the bone is analyzed.

Figure 59 Von Mises criteria derived from the dynamic analysis of the normal anatomy model.

Figure 60 Von Mises criteria derived from the dynamic analysis. It is an agreed criteria of failure in the engineering community, but its application should be scrutinized carefully when the bone is analyzed.

Figure 61 Non connected model. The pillars that represent the zygomatic bone had been hidden to reveal the distribution of Von mises stress below it.

Figure 62 Connected model. The pillars that represent the zygomatic bone had been hidden to reveal the distribution of Von mises stress below it.

Figure 63 Speed without connection. Speed is available only with dynamic studies. Results of this criterion is highly unrealistic due to the main causes, orthotropicity and geometric non linearity.

Figure 64 Speed with connection. Speed is available only with dynamic studies.

Figure 65 Acceleration in the connected model.

Figure 66 Acceleration non-connected model.

Connection	Non-connected		Connected
Base of the virtual parietal	29.4		25.3
virtual Ethmoid base	54.6		34.1
Virtual zygoma base (away)	47.4		46.1
Close zygoma base	41.4		36
Frontozygomatic away	41.7		41.3
Frontozygomatic close	40.1		34.2
Frontoethmoidal away	11		9.6
Frontoethmoidal close	1.6		5.9
Frontoparietal away	1.6		5.9
Frontoparietal close	20.5		17

These values give acceptable clues about deformation magnitude and the extent of the trauma effect upon the socket of the frontal bone and this socket housing. This should be understood in the context of the gradient of stiffness and the staged damaged pattern that is proposed and pre-designed in the anatomical models.

	Away Posterior end of the ethmoid	close Posterior end of the ethmoid
Connected	0.072	0.088

Not connected	0.066	0.125
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This is the acceleration magnitude. The transfer of the same side is high but reach to the away side is lower in the case of non-connected frontal bone. In the case of connected the values are nearly equal which implies higher rate of transfer and implies higher damage. When speaking about the extent of the trauma to the orbit it is sensible to have graded damage and lost eye instead of possible loss of both eyes and fatal brain injury.

Distant side away from the trauma side (dynamic analysis without central connection)

Closer side to the trauma side (dynamic analysis without central connection)

Displacement magnitude of the side of the central discontinuity of the frontal bone without connection. In this dynamic simulation the right side had different maximum values from those of the left side which was denoted on previous graph

Distant side away from the trauma side (dynamic analysis with central connection)

Closer side to the trauma side (dynamic analysis with central connection). Displacement magnitude of the side of the central discontinuity of the frontal bone with connection. Very close values at both sides of the central part of the frontal bone.

Distant side away from the trauma side (dynamic analysis with central connection)

Closer side to the trauma side (dynamic analysis with central connection)

Lateral side of the orbit in the connected model. The connected model had also affect the orbital response to the trauma

Displacement magnitude Lateral side of the orbit in the non-connected model. (**closer to the force application site**)

Displacement magnitude Lateral side of the orbit in the non-connected model. (**distant from the force application site**)

Mechanical reasoning behind the frontal sinus is to provide an extra layer of protection that enhance compliant mechanism. Frontal sinus is extremely important mechanically. Nevertheless, we had not do a separate wok on it yet. This protection should not be thought

as a simple solid barrier. The response of the frontal bone is extremely complex. The response is highly non-linear and very different according to the applied rate or magnitude. The loading of the frontal bone or any other bones, in the axial or appendicular skeleton could be linear or close to linear which is essential to growth. It could be dynamic as a result from traumatic force application. The force could be applied directly to the bone or to indirectly to adjacent bones then transmitted to the specific region via their junction. Occipitofrontalis muscle could play a role in frontal sinus development [10]. Also, the facial musculature could play another significant role in craniofacial growth as well as other parts. All growth patterns need reciprocal movement [11]. Expansion of the head by muscles` effect according to our proposed model should be reversed by another muscle in another direction. In the case of calvaria, this is absent that necessitates another mechanism for initiation and maintenance of the growth. This will be discussed further in the craniofacial growth part. Frontal bone in the case of unclosed metopic suture had not been introduced in a separated paper yet, by we will do it in the next works if the Almighty God will.

Configuration of the bony anatomy should not be approached in a silo thinking manner. The anterior position of the cornea is relative posterior to the superior orbital rim which provides unparalleled protection to the globe. The frontal bone is directly solidly connected to the base of the skull. The skull complex arrangement in addition to the complex orthotropicity of the bone and the force-related factors will determine how the frontal bone fracture will occur. Zygomatic bone, provides about one third of orbital circumference, has a bulk with relatively weaker extensions that anchoring it to its periphery. Its posterior attachment is thin. It had a broad thin attachment medially and corticated attachment superioposteriorly with sphenoid. In the skull, we have three bone types from our biomechanical point of view:

- Thin flat surfaces where they could provide buckling under higher strain rates and possible compliant response under strains with lower rates.
- Larger bone with larger cross section (high mass to outer surface ratio), where compression could provide better mechanical response that fit well in its place. Part of temporal and occipital bone as well as maxillary tuberosity, typically represent this type.
- Almost totally cortical bone with the least medullary space. It had more circular cross section like zygomatic arch and condylar neck

One of the important aspects that should be understood when we study the bone structure is the importance of the medullary bone to initiate bone remodeling, due to its higher cellularity and higher vascularity.

Floor of the orbit had the highest occurring fractures` incidences due to the configuration of the zygoma. The lower wall of the orbit could be fractured causing most preponderant intraorbital soft tissue injury, namely muscle entrapment. Although trapdoor fracture has established its position as an emergency term, its mechanism of occurrence needs to be explained.

The study of fractures of the orbital floor should be preceded by the studying of the thicknesses in all regions of the bony orbit and how it is transitioning from the zygoma which is thick located laterally to the thin area at the medical side. ***There is a combined event, by which buckling fracture plus pressure over the globe that causes intraorbital soft tissue to herniate through this fracture gap. When bone returns to its original place, the fracture slit's sides will return to the original position, it will clip on the orbital content. The return of the open fractured floor is not a local event, but it is a global event that comprises the whole***

midface. What causes orbital content to be herniated is that the hitting object is wide enough to cause bone fracture and pressing on the globe to push the content into the resulting defect. Globe damage could result in such trauma If the trauma was severe.

Persistent frank defects in the orbital floor, simply mean, more complex trauma that leads to form cracking at different sites other than floor of orbit only, with plastic deformations. Its effect on the orbit soft tissue may exceed its out the deformation in the other region. Enophthalmos is a more significant result than unnoticeable loss of malar projection or simple undisplaced zygomatic arch fracture. The theory of explanation of the orbital floor fracture due to transmission of the force via the globe is rejected by the author due to its defective engineering basis and poor modeling and description in the original papers that had introduced this theory. Although the current classification of fractures is based upon the anatomical subunits, this classification needs to be reclassified in another way. Anatomical subunits should be first simplified, then their fracture could be classified according to the engineering deformation that leads to fracture, ***not to the bones that form a specific region.***

Direct blow to the nose could result in trauma that involves ethmoid bone. Accordingly, we prefer to include the nasal bones in the same group of the ethmoid bone fracture. Trauma doesn't know which bone had been fractured.

Better classification of the midface region

- 1) Lateral midface that involves the orbit
- 2) Central midface
- 3) Lower midface that includes maxilla and Lefort classification analogue. Nevertheless, our approach in Aous theory to maxillary fractures could provide a sounder biomechanical description than the current one.

When hitting the zygoma of the right side, next bones may acquire a great amount of energy making the whole craniofacial vibrate. In case of resonance, where natural frequency meets this vibration, the amplitude of displacement in sites distant from the original impaction site could be much higher leading to distant fracture. Oddly in such cases, the zygoma itself had less displacement relatively after that. This traveling by the other bones could lead to raise the third principal stress (tension) in the connection to the traumatized zygoma, resulting in possible separation if the Von mises stress exceeds yield stress. Von mises stress is an accepted criteria of mechanical failure of many materials including bone.

In another words any hit to the zygoma will result in movement of the whole facial skeleton. If the mode change is coordinated with the hit, this would result in a vibration that matches natural frequency causing the highest possible displacement magnitude. Von mises stress would be higher than yield stress ***where any of the three principal stresses could cause failure.*** One should know that this stress causing a fracture is dependent upon their relation to the orthotropicity of the bone.

Studying each cranial bone individually is very important. Detailed studying should include:

- Eigenfrequency
- Effects of its attachments to both hard and soft tissue

This is a very advanced step that needs collaboration with anatomy science specialists and researchers.

In the current paper, we had highlighted the effect of discontinuity in the horizontal part of the frontal bone that is bridged by the cribriform plate of the ethmoidal bone. This will lead to change the response of the orbit to the trauma and the response of the frontal bone itself.

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